

Pre-Questionnaire: Participant Characterization

Demographic Information

A1. Age: _____ years

A2. Country of residence: _____

A3. Highest educational level completed:

- () High school / Technical education
- () Undergraduate (in progress)
- () Undergraduate (completed)
- () Postgraduate / Specialization
- () Master's degree
- () Doctorate

A4. Main field of study: _____

Professional Experience

B1. Total years of experience in software development: _____ years

B2. Years of experience in blockchain development: _____ years _____ months

B3. How do you classify your blockchain experience level?

- () Junior (6 months–2 years)
- () Mid-level (2–5 years)
- () Senior (5+ years)

B4. Current role/title: _____

B5. Type of organization:

- () Blockchain / Web3 startup
- () Traditional tech company
- () Consultancy
- () Freelancer / Independent consultant
- () Academia / Research
- () Other: _____

Blockchain Technical Experience

C1. Which blockchains have you developed on?

(Select all that apply)

- () Ethereum

- () Polygon
- () Binance Smart Chain
- () Solana
- () Avalanche
- () Arbitrum
- () Optimism
- () Hyperledger
- () Others: _____

C2. Programming languages used for blockchain development:

- () Solidity
- () Rust
- () Vyper
- () Go
- () JavaScript / TypeScript
- () Python
- () Move
- () Others: _____

C3. Which Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) platforms have you used?

- () Infura
- () Alchemy
- () Moralis
- () QuickNode
- () Thirdweb
- () Ankr
- () Chainstack
- () AWS Managed Blockchain
- () None
- () Others: _____

C4. How long have you used BaaS platforms?

- () Not using currently
- () Less than 6 months
- () 6 months – 1 year
- () 1–2 years
- () More than 2 years

Project Types

D1. Types of blockchain projects worked on:

- () DeFi (Decentralized Finance)
- () NFTs (Non-Fungible Tokens)

- () DAOs (Decentralized Autonomous Organizations)
- () Blockchain games / GameFi
- () Infrastructure / Tooling
- () Enterprise blockchain
- () Custom smart contracts
- () Cross-chain bridges
- () Oracles
- () Layer 2 solutions
- () Others: _____

D2. Main role in these projects:

- () Smart Contract Developer
- () Full-stack Blockchain Developer
- () Frontend Developer (dApps)
- () Backend Developer (Blockchain integration)
- () Blockchain Architect
- () DevRel Engineer
- () Security / Audit
- () Other: _____

Tools and Practices

E1. Development tools regularly used:

- () Hardhat
- () Truffle
- () Foundry
- () Remix
- () Ganache
- () MetaMask
- () Ethers.js / Web3.js
- () Others: _____